

The Effect of Artificial Intelligence on Iranian EFL Learners' Language Production

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Abstract

This study aimed at finding out whether artificial intelligence generated pictures can increase the amount of language produced by intermediate EFL learners. To this end, sixty Iranian EFL student with an age range of 18 to 25 were selected through convenient sampling method. The aforementioned participants were studying in four different classes, two of which were assigned as the experimental group and the other two ones as the control group. In the activation stage of the lesson, the first group was given some imaginary pictures which have been made by artificial intelligence while the second group used some real pictures downloaded from the internet. The data was gathered on the number of sentences produced by each group. Finally, the data analyzed using independent t-test indicated that the use of artificial intelligence in language learning process led a salient increase in language production. Moreover, the results have pedagogical implications which could be applicable and beneficial in the field of language learning and teaching.

Keywords:

Artificial intelligence, Language learning and production, Engagement study activation

Introduction

The prevalence of artificial intelligence has attracted experts and researchers' attention in every field, even language learning. A number of studies have investigated the possible benefits and effectiveness of the using artificial intelligence in the process of language learning and language production (Patty, 2024). Ling Wei (2023) suggested that AI-mediated instructions positively impact English learning achievement, L2 motivation and self-regulated learning. In addition, As Nicolae Moroianu et al. (2023) stated there are some findings which revealed that the use of AI tools greatly improves students' conceptual understanding. Moreover, AI is making a significant impact in the field of education, particularly in Teaching English as a second language (ELT), since AI-powered tools and technologies are being utilized to create more immersive and engaging learning experiences for students of all grade levels, personalize learning, and provide quick feedback (Cantos et al., 2023). Other studies for instance, Sharma et al. (2019) discovered that AI has been integrated into education through adaptive learning systems, intelligent tutoring systems, and other tools aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of administrative processes, instructional techniques, and the overall learning environment. Moreover, Zou et al. (2023) carried out research in China to investigate the impact of social network-based communication on students' English speaking practice with the help of AI-speaking apps. The study revealed that students had positive attitudes toward interactive activities when they use AI apps to practice spoken English. Additionally, the findings indicated that social network-based interaction within the AI context can greatly improve learners' speaking skills. According to Shevchenko and O.

Ogurtsova (2023) new novel tools such as Google Translate and Chat GPT significantly enhance and simplify the process of language learning for learners. Also, AI-driven language learning platforms used in flipped classrooms assist students by overseeing their pre-class preparation, evaluating their exercises, and offering immediate feedback (Li & Peng, 2022).

Since AI has the efficient potential to cover various aspects of language learning and teaching process, it could play a systematic role in the ESA methodology. ESA stands for engage, study, and activate. The aforementioned learning methodology was developed by Jeremy Harmer (2007) and it is widely used in the TEFL (teaching English as a foreign language) community. ESA methodology contains three main phases: the first phase is the engagement stage in which the teacher introduces the lesson to the class and tries to capture students' attention by creating interest for the topic, to do so the teacher applies various activities such as brainstorming sessions, visuals, imaginations and discussions. The ultimate goal is to activate students' prior knowledge and generate curiosity. The second phase is the study stage in which students are introduced to new language concepts, vocabulary, or grammar structure. Also, guided instruction and models of language use are provided by the teacher and the focus is on helping students to understand and acquire new linguistic information. Finally, the last phase refers to the activation stage where students practice and apply the newly learned language in a communicative and meaningful context. Some activities like paired work interview, picture description, role plays, debates and problem-solving tasks could encourage students' activation process. Also, the teacher provides correction and feedback in order to support students' language development. Among various teaching methodologies in TEFL, ESA claims to be very effective one these days (Aidan, 2020), Also it is somehow different from the previous methods in the process of language teaching and learning.

Due to the increasing interest in applying AI in language learning and teaching, a new field of research seems to emerge. The previous research findings indicated that, the use of AI could promote efficiency and effectiveness in teaching English (Zuriana, 2020). Also, according to Kushmar et al (2022) AI plays a crucial role in enhancing language learning by tailoring the learning process to accommodate the individual talents, backgrounds, and objectives of each student. However, no academic research seems to investigate the use of AI in the ESA methodology of language learning (i.e. applying AI as a tool for facilitating students' engagement and activating their language production by giving students AI-generated pictures). The present study, therefore, is an attempt to find out whether AI (AI image generator) and its generated pictures can increase the amount of language produced by students in the activation phase of ESA methodology, therefore the following research question is set forth:

RQ: Do AI-generated pictures significantly increase the amount of language production of Iranian intermediate EFL learners?

Method

A quasi experimental control group design was applied to address the aforementioned research question. sixty Iranian EFL student with an age range of 18 to 25 were selected through convenient sampling method. The aforementioned participants were studying in four different classes, two of which were assigned as the experimental group and the other two ones as the control group.

2.1 Participants

Sixty Iranian EFL intermediate male and female learners, age 18-25 were selected through convenient sampling method. Their level of proficiency was considered intermediate based on the hierarchy of institute, so there was no need for homogeneity test. The participants were assigned into two groups; the first group was the experimental group which included 31 students (in two classes, one with 15 students and the other one with 16 students), the second group was the control group which consisted of 29 students (the students were from two classes, one with 14 students and another one with 15 students).

2.2 Materials and instruments

To fulfill the purpose of the study, the following instruments were utilized.

2.2.1 AI image generator

According to Dennis(2024) “An AI Image Generator is a type of software application that uses artificial intelligence (AI) and [machine learning \(ML\) techniques](#) to create or generate new images. These AI image generators can create images from scratch or transform existing images into new ones by using various algorithms and techniques.” In the current study, the Microsoft image generator was used. The instrument generates photo from a given description. In this regard, the researchers gave some descriptions about several super animals and their extraordinary characteristics to the aforementioned software. The descriptions were originated from the researchers’ imagination in the case of super animals’ physical characteristics for instance their body and their appearance, their life style (e.g. whether they are carnivores or haunter) and their abilities (e.g. they can fly or swim). The results were some unique pictures which incredibly affect the students’ activation and production.

2.2.2 Description task

To give the learners the opportunity to apply the acquired structures in their language production in the activation phase, a context was developed. As an example, after presenting and practicing “might for possibility”, the learners were asked to describe some possibilities, but in this case, there was a difference between the experimental group and the control group. The experimental group were asked to describe some AI-generated imaginary pictures of traces left in the nature to guess what had happened, while the learners in the control group were supposed to describe some real pictures downloaded from internet.

2.3 Procedure

As it was stated in the introduction section, The ESA methodology was applied to the present study. In this regard, all four classes were introduced to the target structures through ESA methodology and its phases (engage, study, activation). For the sake of validity, the 4 classes were managed by the same teacher, however, in the activation stage of the lesson the experimental group was given some AI-generated pictures, then, they were asked to describe and talk about the pictures. In contrast, the control group had to use some real pictures. After setting the context, the teacher asked learners to think for one minute and then share their ideas with their partners. In both of the groups, one learner in each pair was responsible to record the voice during the interaction. The study took two weeks (four sessions) and four different grammatical items were presented to the learners. The data was gathered at the end of each session and the number of sentences produced by each participant was counted. It worth mentioning that each embedded clause was considered as a sentence. The number of sentences in each session were added up and the final result was considered as the final score for each student.

2.4 Data analysis

The number of sentences produces by each student were primary for measuring their amount of language production. Since there were two sets of scores from two different groups, an independent t-test was run to see if there is any significant difference between the groups.

Results

The research question claimed to investigate the amount of language produced by Iranian intermediate EFL learners with the use of AI (do AI-generated pictures significantly increase the amount of language production of Iranian intermediate EFL learners?), in order to answer this question, the frequency is calculated for each student. The following table1 summarizes the students’ performance in each group.

Table 1 presents the amount of mean difference between the total number of sentences produced by the experimental and the control group. Also, in order to check the normality of the data and controlling the outliers Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk were run. The results revealed that the data were normal in both groups and there were no outliers. As it is obvious, the mean of the experimental group (35.0968) is greater than the control group’s mean (24.7241).

Table 1

Students' performance based on the number of produced sentences

Experimental	31	35.0968	4.61414	8.2872
Control	29	24.7241	6.13478	1.13920

An independent samples t-test was conducted to determine whether there were differences between the two groups' performance in terms of frequency (number of sentences which have been produced by each student). As table 2 indicates significant differences were found between the scores of both groups (Sig=.000, $p<.5$). Therefore, the participants' language production in the experimental group is much more than the control groups' production.

Table 2

Independent samples t-test, investigating the differences between the scores of both groups

t-test for equality of means

Levene's test for equality 95%confidence
of variances interval of the

	F	Sig	df	(two-tailed)	difference	Sig.	Mean	Std.error	difference
					lower				upper
Production	1.808	.184	7.433	58.000	10.37264	1.39555	7.57913	13.16614	
	7.363	51.909	.000	10.37264	1.40874	7.54567	13.19961		

Discussion and conclusion

The current study sought to examine the impact of using AI-generated pictures on Iranian EFL learners' language production. The results revealed that applying AI-generated pictures was more effective in increasing EFL learners' language production in comparison with using real pictures. By considering the outperformance of the experimental group in the amount of language production, it could be interpreted that the use of AI in the process of language learning will boost the learners' creativity which results in more language production and engagement.

The findings of the study corroborate those of Zhang (2022) who investigated the Artificial Intelligence technology and its role in autonomous English language learning. Following Zhang's study, the findings in the present study in this regard might reveal more engagement and enthusiasm toward the AI and its tools for language learners in comparison with the common used tools (real pictures or other tools). So this may lead to more autonomy and better performance in the case of language production. Similarly, the findings were in line with those of Song and Song (2022) who found significant improvements in both writing skills and motivation among the students who were exposed to AI-assisted instruction, according to them the aforementioned students exhibited enhanced proficiency in various aspects of writing such as organization, coherence, grammar and vocabulary. In a similar vein, Ferhan Girgin Sağın et al. (2023) advocated the idea of embracing AI with knowledge, promoting AI proficiency among teachers and students, using AI ethically in educational environments, and staying involved with the advancing AI technologies. This will ensure that AI resources are utilized to enhance critical thinking and make a positive impact on education and society. The findings of the study corroborate those of Marzuki et al. (2023) who investigated many AI writing tools used in

teaching English as a Foreign Language and shed light on how teachers use them to help students with writing challenges. Tools like Quillbot, Jenni, Chat-GPT, WordTune, Copy.ai, Paperpal, and Essay writer were found to create a better learning environment and boost students' academic skills. Also, the findings of the study were in agreement with those of Wu (2024) who investigated the impact of AI-based writing tools on the quality of students' writing and found that the tools have proven to be effective in improving writing skills. Similarly, Chen et al. (2020) found that AI is having a significant impact on education especially in the areas of management, instruction and learning, in addition, AI has enabled customization and personalization of learning materials based on students' needs and capabilities, thus providing students with a better learning experience.

Finally, it seems using AI-generated pictures help and enable EFL learners to produce more sentences in the activation stage of the lesson, besides it makes students more engaged in the class and this will lead to more language production. In particular, the results strongly recommend EFL teachers to apply AI tools more in their teaching process, however, AI and its tools have some short comes. According to Al-Bakri (2021) there are certain drawbacks associated with this, including the potential for job loss and ethical considerations surrounding the use of artificial intelligence. In addition, Barak and Dori (2019) stated that artificial intelligence offers numerous advantages in the instruction of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics, including delivering tailored learning experiences, increasing student engagement, and automating repetitive tasks. Nevertheless, this also presents certain difficulties, such as the requirement for extensive teacher training and the potential for biases in artificial intelligence algorithms.

In sum, due to the widespread use of Artificial intelligence these days, this study was an attempt to investigate the impact of using AI-generated pictures on the Iranian intermediate EFL learners' language production. The findings indicated that the utilization of AI-generated pictures proved to be more successful in enhancing the language production of EFL learners in comparison with the use of authentic pictures.

It can be inferred that integrating AI into language learning and teaching can enhance learners' creativity, leading to increased language production and engagement. The present study strongly suggests the EFL teachers to make use of AI-generated tools and apply them in their classrooms, however, this application requires special training and flexibility toward artificial intelligence and its components.

Ultimately, there are some limitations in the present study which can be addressed in the future studies. For first, the present study adopted a small number of intermediate EFL learners, thus no generalizable conclusion can be drawn from the findings. In this regard, future researchers are recommended to adopt more students with different levels of proficiency. Secondly, there are various tools of artificial intelligence which have the possible potential to change the whole process of language teaching, while the present study applied just one of the aforementioned tools. Finally, the study took two weeks and only four grammatical items were taught to the learners, since the language teaching process includes different aspects and components the future studies could investigate other aspects of this process with more duration.

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